

ISic3124

I.Sicily inscription 3124

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

statue base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2011.06.16; 2013.10.02

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance

excavations in vicinity of agora

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 82534

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI330715

1. ὁ δᾱμος τῶν Ταυρομενιτᾱν
2. Νυμφόδωρον Εὐκλείδα Αρεθ.
3. εὐνοίας ἔνεκεν.
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645465

PHI 330715

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 32.0937

Bacci, G. M. 1980-1981. Ricerche a Taormina negli anni 1977-1980. *Kokalos*. 26-27: 737-748. At 739-740 dr

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3124. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388159>